

A Study on Changes in Sensitivities in Business Management during and After the Pandemic Process

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Abstract

The epidemic created chaos all over the world with millions of people affected; preventive measures were implemented, which led to a decrease in economic activity. The rapid and widespread spread of the virus caused the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare COVID-19 a global emergency on February 20, 2020, and then a pandemic on March 11, 2020. Risks in financial markets reflect the expected losses shown in pr research (Al-Awadhi et al., 2020; Ashraf, 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Onali, 2020). All major exchanges saw losses in the double-digit percentage range, with the S&P 500 falling 30 percent in just 16 trading days. Baker et al. (2020) claimed that the spread of the Coronavirus from China to other countries and the ensuing pandemic created a drop in yields and more volatility in financial markets. This was because the pandemic was triggered by the pandemic. Current levels of market volatility in the United States are comparable to those seen in the 2008, 1987 and early 1930s (Baker et al., 2020). The fluctuations in the predictability of financial markets raise serious doubts about the accuracy of Fama's efficient market hypothesis (EMH), developed at the beginning of the 20th century (1970). According to

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EMH, investors cannot predict changes in the value of assets based on information on previous trading activities of stocks. Even if there are studies that give confidence in EMH, a significant number of researchers have concluded that security prices are predictable because market conditions create a certain degree of predictability in security returns. In addition, the ideas of EMH and behavioral finance combined in Lo's (2004) AMH provide an excellent explanation for changes in the degree of return predictability. This study is an examination of the changes in the sensitivities in the business management during and after the pandemic process and includes literature reviews.

Keywords: *Business Management, Business Management Sensitivities, Business Management During the Pandemic Process, Business Management After the Pandemic, Changes in Business Management Sensitivities*

1. Introduction

According to Lo (2004), financial markets go through periods when their performance, efficiency and volatility fluctuate to varying degrees. Also, because of adoption, investors' preferences change over time, meaning that previous price movements have an impact on current prices, which is directly in opposition to the EMH. As a result, the predictability of returns shows cyclical patterns because of information technology, macroeconomic institutions, and market rules and policies. This shows that the adaptive market hypothesis (AMH) is correct. In addition, Lo (2004) argues that market evolution occurs because of panics, bubbles, and crises. Recently, financial markets have been affected by events related to Covid-19. These latest events are the main impetus for the decision to conduct the proposed investigation. A year ago, no one had considered the possibility of living as we do now. Researchers' focus has now shifted to the impact of Covid-19 on financial market performance and volatility.

Due to the potential for shocks from Covid-19 in financial markets to confirm AMH, we decided to focus on this issue. According to this idea, markets go through stages that can be predicted to varying degrees according to market conditions. Similarly, COVID-19 covers several periods

(Wagner, 2020) in the first phase of the pandemic, which is the incubation phase of the pandemic. At this stage, only knowledgeable and knowledgeable investors can partially predict the future of financial markets and investment trends. In the second phase, also known as the epidemic phase, there is an increase in the amount of interest shown by investors to the topic of Coronavirus through Google search and conference calls. Finally, investors understand that the virus has the potential to directly harm them and that the financial markets are very volatile during the fever phase. In the first step of this process, to determine whether the COVID-19 commodity markets exhibit adaptive behavior, the second step involves using linear and non-linear econometric models to determine whether the changing behavior of the markets resulted in lucrative prospecting during the pandemic.

2. How COVID-19 Shocks Interact with the Adaptive Market Hypothesis

This work contributes in several ways to broadening the structure of previous research on how COVID-19 shocks interact with the adaptive market hypothesis. First, the aim of this research is to explore the relationship between the Adaptive Market Hypothesis and the changing behavior of commodity indices during the COVID-19 crisis. The Adaptive Market Hypothesis allows returns on investment in commodities to fluctuate over time. Second, most of the research conducted in COVID-19 focuses on the behavior of stock markets, but there is no study that addresses the behavior of commodities markets and can come to a range of conclusions. Third, the current research is the first of its kind to investigate the behavior of commodity returns in a variety of common COVID-19 settings. The purpose of this research is to determine which of these situations is more beneficial for the performance of these goods. Based on the findings of this research, returns from financial commodities markets appear to exhibit adaptive behavior during COVID-19 and interact with the shocks created by the COVID-19 phases. Below is a description of the structure of the thesis: in the next section we will discuss the literature; In the section under "Methods", we discuss data disclosure and methodology. Data analysis is presented in the "Results" section, and the conclusion and discussion are presented in the "Conclusion" section.

Due to COVID-19, the economy and financial markets around the world have entered a cycle. As COVID-19 progresses through the epidemic (Li et al., 2020) and pandemic (Ashraf, 2020) stages, the lives of billions of people around the world are affected by the disease, causing a shift in economic activities (Dunford et al., 2020). According to Gates (2020), major COVID-19 outbreaks have severely affected many countries, including the United States, China, Iran, Italy, France, and Spain, as well as the United Kingdom and France. According to the findings of several studies, infectious diseases have a negative impact on economies by causing financial market crashes during contagious seasons (see, for example, Lee and McKibbin, 2004; Chen et al., 2007; Baker et al., 2012; Bai, 2014; Macciocchi et al. others, 2016; Del-Giudice and Paltrinieri, 2017; Chen et al., 2018). Goodell (2020) conducted groundbreaking research that provides a complete literature review showing the financial impacts of natural disasters such as climate change, conflicts, and location-restricted disasters. It shows that the COVID-19 pandemic has damaged both local and global economies and is associated with poor performance of financial markets, banking, and insurance sector. He goes on to say that the COVID-19 era is rich in opportunities for conducting future research in financial markets.

3. Direct Link Between Impact of COVID-19 and Stock Market Returns

Similarly, Al-Awadhi et al. (2020) provides evidence of a direct link between the impact of COVID-19 and stock market returns. Using China data collected from individual firms, they assess the early impact of the COVID-19 outbreak on share prices in China. They concluded that there is a significant inverse relationship between the increased number of deaths and the returns from the shares of the firms they work with. Liu et al. (2020) examines the short-term impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on financial market indices from 21 different countries. According to the Footnote 2 Findings, the countries most severely affected by COVID-19 are the United Kingdom, Italy, Germany, the United States, Singapore, Korea, and Japan. Onali (2020) applies the GARCH (1,1) model to find out how the number of deaths caused by COVID-19 affects the Dow Jones and S&P500 indices in the US and six other countries. The research reveals that, apart from the deaths reported in China, the deaths had little effect on the volatility of financial markets in the US.

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Similarly, Zhang et al. (2020) discovered that the reason for the increase in risk posed by global financial markets is COVID-19. Ashraf (2020) conducted research to assess the impact of proven deaths on the financial markets of 64 countries during the period starting on 22 January 2020 and ending on 17 April 2020. He discovers a negative correlation between the death rate and the volatility of financial markets, showing that returns decrease as the number of fatalities increases. Ali et al. (2020) explores the impact of COVID-19 on various indices of the financial sector, including bitcoin, bond indices, stock indices and commodity indices. They use the E-GARCH model to analyze the volatility in these indices over various sample periods and conclude that the markets in China remain stable.

Baker et al. (2020) analyzes the pandemic impact of COVID-19 on financial markets in the USA and compares the impact of COVID-19 with the impact of previous pandemics. Compared with previous infectious disease pandemics that occurred in 1918–19, 1957–19 and 1968, the researchers found that government restrictions on business activities and voluntary social distancing during COVID-19 had a very strong effect. The impact on the volatility of financial markets in the USA. Alfaro et al. (2020) analyzes data from the United States and concludes that the stock market has fallen in response to pandemics such as Covid-19 and SARS. In contrast, the behavior of global markets has been shown to be more volatile over the several periods studied in this research. Using the Google Trend Synthetic Index, Papadamou et al. (2020) explores the impact of the pandemic on the financial markets of AsiaFootnote4, Australia, EuropeFootnote5, Russia, United Kingdom, and United States. According to their findings, the search queries for the term COVID-19 and the COVID-19 concern from Google directly affect the volatility of financial markets due to pandemic conditions. They also found that this effect was felt more strongly in European countries than in other sample countries. Despite this, there is a discernible upward trend in the average volatility of financial markets in the United States, United Kingdom and Germany as COVID-19 progresses from epidemic to pandemic stage. Shahid et al. (2020a), AMH is supported by the fact that commodities markets experience periods of high predictability followed by periods of no predictability. Okorie and Lin (2021) discovered that the COVID-19 pandemic has a fractal contagion effect on financial markets. Günay (2021), focusing on foreign exchange markets, draws parallels between COVID-19 and the Global Financial Crisis (CFC). In terms of

overall volatility spillover, he discovered, the shockwave caused by the pandemic is almost eight times greater than that caused by the GFC.

Lin and Su (2021) explore the return pattern of energy commodities and find that commodity markets have experienced significant changes throughout the pandemic. According to Zaremba et al. (2021) surveyed 49 countries and showed that government interventions (such as the closure of businesses and schools) have a modest effect on the liquidity of stock markets. Okorie and Lin (2021) explore the impact of the pandemic on four main financial markets originating from the most affected regions (Brazil, India, Russia, and the USA). They see no difference in the way they behave in terms of the returns of the markets in Brazil and the United States. As a result of the pandemic, they discovered that financial markets in Russia are more efficient than those in India. Al-Refai et al. (2022) analyzes the effects of shocks caused by COVID-19 and changes in oil prices on GCC financial markets using the Kalman filter. They conclude that all financial markets in the GCC, except for Oman, will respond more strongly to oil price changes and the COVID pandemics, both positively and negatively, after March 2020. Matos et al. (2021) explores the link between the number of confirmed deaths that occurred in Hubei, China, during the COVID-19 pandemic, and returns from the S&P 500 index . Using partial coherences for Granger-causality in the quantile technique, they discover that mortality has a negative effect on the returns from the S&P-500 index.

4. The Three Most Important Sub-sectors of the Economy

We select the most actively traded commodities on the Chicago Board of Options Exchange (CBOE) from the three most important subsectors of the economy: agriculture, energy, and precious metals. (“COVID-19 and adaptive behavior of returns: evidence from commodity ...”) All these sub-sectors are interconnected. We use DataStream to collect data. The time range covered by the data is from December 2, 2019, to December 31, 2020.

If markets are flexible, the pattern of commodity returns should alternate between periods of independence and confidence (see Shahid and Mehmood, 2015; Shahid and Sattar, 2017; Shahid

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et al., 2018, 2020b). We divided the sampling period into many different sub-samples to investigate how the commodity return changed over time. To begin, it is correct to divide the example into COVID-19 Outbreak, Pandemic (according to Haroon and Rizvi, 2020) and Endemic stages. Second, time periods that include deaths from COVID-19 in China, Europe, and the United States (based on Al-awadhi et al., 2020; Haroon and Rizvi, 2020). As a result, the three time periods associated with deaths can be given the following names: Fatal1 (for deaths in China), Fatal2 (for deaths in Europe), and Fatal3 (for deaths in the US and around the world).

On the other hand, while most agricultural indices show negative returns in the epidemic and pandemic stages of the disease, all agricultural indices provide positive returns in the endemic stage of the disease, except for feeder cattle. Surprisingly, all energy indicators yield negative returns during the epidemic phase. However, throughout the pandemic and endemic stages, this behavior changes and becomes positive, which is a positive marker of AMH. On the other hand, most indices that track precious metals produce returns that are negative during an epidemic but positive during the other two phases of the cycle. In Figure 1, daily returns over the entire sampling period are shown for each commodity. Figures 2 and 3 show correlated commodity returns for the three different industries that are the focus of this research.

According to the findings of Ghazani and Ebrahimi (2019), it would be appropriate to start by performing a Generalized Spectral (GS) test using a one-month sliding window to investigate the various behavioral patterns demonstrated by commodity returns during the COVID-19 crisis. The GS test can simultaneously capture both linear and nonlinear forms of dependency. Additionally, we use linear and nonlinear tests to determine the degree of predictability (profitable opportunities) and the adaptive behavior suggested by commodity return (Urquhart and Hudson, 2013; Shahid et al., 2019a). This research was conducted by Urquhart and Hudson (2013) and Shahid et al. (2019a) made by The Generalized Spectral (GS) test is used to analyze how indices change over time.

It is correct to use the non-parametric Generalized Spectral (GS) test (Escanciano and Velasco, 2006) and it is necessary to correlate the time-varying behavior of commodities with predation levels independently through linear and nonlinear models. This allows us to reveal linear and nonlinear relations. Assuming that Y_t is a stationary time series, and the martingale difference

series cannot predict future returns, then the null hypothesis of a martingale difference series is that it does not exist.

For many Covid phases, most indices experience periods of significant predictability followed by periods of no predictability. Agricultural indices (excluding agriculture-livestock and live cattle) exhibit insignificant autocorrelation, suggesting the lack of predictability of returns during the COVID-19 pandemic. On the other hand, during the pandemic period, returns are dependent and highly predictable. Following this, the behavior returns, and it is impossible to predict returns during the endemic period. All precious metals except copper and all energy indices except unleaded gasoline exhibit the same return pattern. Yields from live cattle are predictable during the pandemic and endemic phases of the disease, but not during the epidemic phase. Copper and unleaded gasoline are predicted during the epidemic and pandemic phases of the disease, but not in the endemic phase supporting AMH. Using the Runs test yields returns on soybeans and sugar produced by agriculture, but most indices from the other two sectors experience periods of predictability after periods of lack of predictability in COVID-19 market conditions. Therefore, defending the AMH. According to the ratio of variance test, returns from most indices can be estimated in pandemic and endemic COVID-19 environments, but returns cannot be predicted during the epidemic phase; therefore, the findings of linear tests support AMH.

Using the BDS test, it shows a significant nonlinear prediction (at 5%) during pandemics, but no nonlinear prediction during epidemic or endemic periods. Profits from the sale of commodities show a significant amount of non-linear forecast during epidemic and pandemic stages, but no non-linear forecast at endemic stage. On the other hand, although these returns are predictable under pandemic conditions and endemic conditions of COVID-19, returns from palladium, declining energy and unleaded gasoline are not predicted under epidemic conditions. The findings of nonlinear BDS tests largely support AMH and are consistent with research (Urquhart and Hudson, 2013; Ghazani and Araghi, 2014; Shahid et al., 2019a).

5. Times of Predictability That Gives AMH Confidence

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We are getting some fascinating findings from the death stages of Covid-19, as the bulk of commodities move between times of predictability that gives AMH confidence and times of no predictability. According to the autocorrelation test findings, it is not possible to predict the returns of agricultural livestock, agricultural index, beef cattle, live cattle, and wheat. In addition, metal indices such as hot oil, non-energy oil, gold, metal, silver, palladium, nickel, and zinc are unpredictable in the first two consecutive stages of death (fatal1 and deadly2), but predictable in the third stage (fatal3). Our findings show a consistent pattern of behavior for soybeans, palladium, and platinum in trial testing. However, unleaded gasoline tested using the VR method, as well as coffee, cocoa, live cattle, soybeans, wheat, oil, and oil tested using the BDS method, are predictable during phases 2 and 3, while they remain unexpected at phase 1 deadly1. Commodity indices (corn, soybeans, reduced energy, oil, unleaded gasoline, unnatural gasoline, and platinum) revert to phase lethal1, phase lethal2 unexpected behavior followed by lethal phase. In VR testing, commodities exhibit comparable behavior. Other commodity indices similarly experience periods of great predictability in some Fatal phases and periods of unpredictability in other Fatal phases, giving weight to the argument that AMH is correct. In conclusion, we show that certain market situations can provide lucrative business opportunities, such as those created by the epidemic, pandemic, and death stages. As a result, the second objective, to explore how the changing behavior of the markets can provide a forecast for monetization opportunities during COVID-19, has been successfully accomplished. Furthermore, our findings are consistent with those found in research (Ramrez et al., 2015; Shahid et al., 2019c) showing how markets change in response to certain conditions or crises.

This research explores the degree to which commodity markets are affected by AMH as AMH absorbs or participates in changing returns behavior during the epidemic, pandemic, endemic and mortal shocks (stages) of COVID-19. We show that AMH is responsible for explaining the commodity markets response to the COVID-19 sub-phases. We are applying Generalized Spectral (GS) testing to daily data from the Chicago Board of Options Exchange (CBOE) in the United States to identify examples of adaptive behavior exhibited in commodity markets during COVID-19. This daily data consists of well-known and most traded commodities. In addition, we leverage

linear and nonlinear econometric models to determine whether the changing behavior of markets can produce an estimate of their probability of making a profit during COVID-19.

During the COVID-19 era, we found that most of the commodities examined had positive returns. In a more in-depth analysis, only a small number of commodities were determined to be predictable during the full sample COVID-19 period using autocorrelation and run testing. On the other hand, most commodities are more predictable using linear VR and non-linear BDS testing, which are indicators of the inefficiency of commodity markets. During the epidemic and endemic phases, most of the indices of all three industries lack predictability, but during the pandemic phases this behavior pattern is reversed. Similarly, while indices are estimated in certain COVID-19 conditions (outbreak, pandemic, and endemic), they are not predicted in others, even when using linear and nonlinear econometric models. This is the case regardless of whether the condition is an epidemic, pandemic or endemic. On the other hand, commodity returns are significant during some phases of the COVID-19 death phase, while in other segments they are minimal. Overall, the results of our research show that the deadly and pandemic stages of COVID-19 are met with a quick response from the commodity markets.

As a result, commodity returns exhibit time-varying behavior during COVID-19, and this changing behavior creates profitable opportunities in the market under certain COVID-19 conditions. According to the adaptive market hypothesis (AMH), which claims that returns from financial markets go through periods of significant predictability and little predictability because of certain market conditions, bubbles, panics and crises, the behavior of COVID-19 shocks is best illustrated by the adaptive market hypothesis (AMH). is explained. Finally, it is appropriate to contribute to the growing research on COVID-19 by first investigating how the behavior of commodity returns interacts with COVID-19 while operating under the auspices of the AMH .

6. Systematization Procedure

systematization procedure , preliminary dimensions allow us to juxtapose similar articles and make intra-category comparisons that result in new and more complex dimensions. Some of these

dimensions, developed inductively through content analysis, not only retrospectively summarize the current focal points of the articles selected to answer our initial research question, but also refer prospectively to emerging trends regarding the post-pandemic "New Normal". These can be considered prospective "overarching categories" [35] that expand and develop other literature reviews on the basis from which the study began .

7. Coping Mechanisms

One of the main lines running through the sample is coping mechanisms, namely, survival strategic maneuvers in the era of COVID-19. Building on a review of the available literature , Wenzel et al presented a general classification of these mechanisms: *i.e., savings, conservation, innovation, and exit* . Similarly, Bailey and Breslin suggested that proactive approaches and rapid innovation “may be the best bet for the resilience of many organizations.” (“The Future of Business Education: A Commentary in the ... - ResearchGate”) As for innovation, in many studies business model innovations were the counterpart of strategic responses; The innovation has also been repeatedly suggested as an excellent solution using various compounds such as open, convergence systemic, accelerated, AI-enabled and bricolage innovations. Also, on the one hand, at the theoretical level, several authors have proposed some general strategic trends that may prove to be effective in combating COVID-19, such as systems perspectives, interdisciplinary strategies.

8. Corporate Strategy

One of the main lines running through the sample is coping mechanisms, namely, survival strategic maneuvers in the era of COVID-19 . Building on a review of the available literature , Wenzel et al presented a general classification of these mechanisms: *i.e., savings, conservation, innovation, and exit* . Similarly, Bailey and Breslin suggested that proactive approaches and rapid innovation “may be the best bet for the resilience of many organizations.” (“The Future of Business Education: A Commentary in the ... - ResearchGate”) Evidence from retailers, pharmaceutical companies and tech giants is important to discuss the “heterogeneity of collaboration strategies” in large-scale

emergencies. He suggests that the transboundary dynamics of COVID-19 could lead to “institution-environment mismatch” and possibly uncertainty suffocation. This recurring theme was developed by the authors to refer to the sudden death of a business due to the escalation of genres and the degree of uncertainty. (“COVID-19 and business failures: The paradoxes of experience, scale, and ...”) Some antecedents of uncertainty drowning are discussed in the literature : confusion between risk and uncertainty – particularly Knightian/fundamental uncertainty, paradoxical components of uncertainty management, legacy framing and dominant mindsets and fixed beliefs market priority/logic, and/or the global business ecosystem. Also, in relation to the risk society, the unfolding of broader and societal conceptualizations of risk requires a reexamination of organizational critical signification and the boundary between reasonable/incredible to obtain different "modes of operation".

To address this shifting essence of risk, Brammer et al. suggested that the dialectic between work and society should be explored through "a more detailed and dynamic concept of society." (“The COVID-19 pandemic: how can risk science help? - ResearchGate”) In doing so, they used socialization theory to analyze the impact of COVID-19 in the US and predicted three post-pandemic scenarios for the role of business in society. Similarly, translating deep uncertainty into situations in which traditional risk management can be applied has been discussed as a possible antidote to uncertainty suffocation. More generally, considering changing public perceptions of risk and more effective risk communication tools are vital prerequisites for any uncertainty management practice.

9. Preparation Concepts

There is a traceable stock of descriptive terms put forward by several authors to refer to the capacity of organizations to rein in shocks. We call these descriptive terms preparatory cognomens. These include, but are not limited to , strategic hypermobility, resilience, agility, robustness, adaptability, and anti-frailty platform ecosystem resilience, organizational. Knowledge, versatility, tight-loose versatility, productive flexibility through multimodality, and corporate hybridity are examples. Beyond these theoretical descriptive terms, some studies have attempted to

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functionalize some of these preparatory cognomen. For example, Mertzanis suggested a possible operationalization of country-level preparedness in the context of COVID-19: *the epidemiological sensitivity risk index "to predict worldwide corporate performance"*.

Similarly, Tosun et al investigated the immunizing effect of previous disaster exposure in New York-based firms and concluded that firms that survived 9/11 also performed approximately 7% better in terms of stock returns during the COVID-19 pandemic. Finally, Davidsson et al. [124] criticized the “pervasive discourse” produced and disseminated by both academics and practitioners for framing COVID-19 negatively “in terms of failure, resilience and crisis” [124]; instead, they argued, the virus could be conceptualized as an "external activator" to catalyze constructive change. The failure of over-reliance on just-in-time systems, outages in SCs, challenges and factors influencing their behavior during pandemics had a strong presence on set. Its redesign and localization have been discussed many times. While discussing the survival strategies of SCs and key SC strategies for the post-COVID era, the urgent need for digital SC twins [88] and the creation of what we call supply chain vigilance was strongly emphasized.

supply chain vigilance, advanced technologies (IoT, blockchain, artificial intelligence , deep and machine learning, RFID, and others), the literature review allows SCs to "predict early surprise signals" and "act faster." “He claimed it helped. Ivanov and Dolgui emphasized that the future competition will be between information services and the analytical algorithms behind SCs, namely their vigilance. Several manuscripts spoke of the role of various factors/ideas in specific contexts and explored the contribution of purpose, additive manufacturing clusters, reorganization, collaboration, alliance management/artificial intelligence. , digital technologies, sensing and capture capabilities, chaos theory and the appropriate management of SCs during the COVID-19 era have introduced innovation to “bring service near your home”.

Fasan empirically showed that companies equipped with green SC management suffered less in terms of stock returns during the crisis. (“Supply chain agility responding to unprecedented changes: empirical ...”) Finally, in an editorial comment, Ketchen and Craighead provided some anecdotal evidence of how firms are leveraging interdisciplinary strategy by combining research from entrepreneurship, SC management and strategic management . As for SC localization, a few

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researchers have considered the De-China of SCs, the emergence of "China for China" or "America for America" supply ecosystems, and multiple Samsung-like supply ecosystems. - resource production registered as viable future options. Shorter supply chains and the tendency to buy local products can be an important factor in making supply chains flexible and sustainable.

Finally, the pandemic has magnified a series of last-mile delivery challenges that could lead to the widespread implementation of more innovative and sustainable avenues such as drone delivery in the future. During the crisis, the decisive role of senior leadership and key leadership practices adopted by leaders such as Jacinda Ardern and Tsai Ing-wen underlined the importance of women's participation in leadership positions. Wilson reviewed some lessons from New Zealand's approach to COVID-19 and presented a pandemic leadership framework characterized by nurturing a common purpose, driven by expertise, aligning collective efforts, enabling coping, and building confidence in leadership. Kniffin et al. in line with this, he concluded that a feminine leadership style is likely to be considered an optimal choice for crisis management. As an example, statistical analysis of data from 210 countries has shown that gender equality and the proportion of women in the legislature have a positive impact on public health outcomes in the context of COVID-19.

The characteristics of effective crisis leadership and the factors affecting it have been explored by several authors. In this context, ethical leadership, authentic leadership, and flexible leadership based on pragmatic idealism from different leadership styles are examined theoretically. Crisis leaders recognize the importance of transparent, compassionate, and empathetic communication, prioritize improvisation, demonstrate supra-dynamic managerial abilities, adapt leadership styles to context, and introduce a complexity. Also, due to the unprecedented virtualization of organizational work, Chamakiotis insisted on reimagining e-Leadership and proposed a framework for e-Leadership in the context of COVID-19; Similarly, Kulshreshtha and Sharma listed the pros and cons of e-leadership. Finally, two survey-based studies in Germany reported the positive impact of health-oriented leadership and the effectiveness of task- and relationship-oriented leadership on employee job performance.

10. Conclusion

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It would be correct to specify three categories (corporate strategy, corporate design and culture and contextual environment) and 13 subcategories. Notable impacts include CoVsumption, uncertainty drowning, Sustainability 2022, 14, 9820 24/32 meta-firm normalization, and the increasing importance of supply chain vigilance. Despite COVID-19 being labeled as the wildcard or black swan event in our selection, most publications have described COVID-19 as an "accelerator" or "catalyst" of pre-existing trends such as workplace transformation. Surveillance technologies, capitalism's pursuit of transformation, digitalization, virtualization, corporate social responsibility, structural inequality, distancing from globalization and e-commerce are just a few of them. In addition to acceleration, the imagination of collectively desired futures and greater convergence of seemingly unrelated technologies, objects, ideas, and activities were two other recurring main motifs. As strategic stances, our study produced sufficient evidence to support the notion that survival and adaptation strategies take precedence over shaping strategies. The necessity of new value propositions and the emphasis on corporate social impact can be considered an opportunity to debunk the grand narrative of neo-liberalism and move towards achieving sustainable development goals. Alongside the outlined research guidelines, the study revealed areas related to the strategic management of organizations that require further attention and consideration:

- (i) *frameworks for assessing organizational readiness in the face of Knightian uncertainty.*
- (ii) *Identifying the characteristics of uncertainty-ready organizations.*
- (iii) *Adapting to shaping strategic postures during major disruptions and*
- (iv) *The importance of identifying and capturing borderline opportunities in changing the direction of organizations' strategic path. Needless to say, "given the lack of priority", academic attempts to understand the effects of the crisis "demand frequent renewal" as time goes on.*

Future research should try to combine multiple databases that are likely to capture non-indexed journals from the two databases used. In addition to the initial limitation, the time frame also excluded some new releases. Accordingly, as the field of COVID -related research in business and management continues to grow, future studies may extend the timeframe to include more recent

studies . Future work may extend the time frame and focus on other social science areas to synthesize the literature . In addition, although predetermined categories facilitated the review process, unexpected categories/concepts that emerged may have been overlooked. However, we argue that this example represents the current literature on COVID-19 in business and management . One recommendation is a comprehensive examination of the contextual environment of organizations for the social, technological, environmental, economic, technological, and political drivers of change triggered by COVID-19 to recognize the seeds of change and key uncertainties for the post-COVID-19 “New-Normal”. We hope this study of the impacts of COVID-19 on business and management will serve as a catalyst for new lines of research on the nature and impact of COVID-19 and other pandemics on business operations and strategies.

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